

Popular Problems

This resource is used in the second study for phase 2. Developers use this to remember a recent debugging scenario they experienced.

1. Facing a bug in **production**.
2. **Concurrency-related** bug: **Race condition, deadlocks, synchronization**.
 - 2.1. **E.g., Heisenberg's multithreading**: A **multithreaded application with race conditions** happening between threads
3. A bug that is related to an **external component or library**, meaning that you do not own the defective component.
4. A bug in an **unfamiliar or very huge codebase** (someone else's codebase.)
5. A bug related to **libraries or dependencies** that are or are **no longer supported or maintained**.
6. A bug in a **legacy** codebase with minimal documentation.
7. An issue with a code base that has been **optimized by the compiler**.
8. A bug related to a single event that is initiated by the user and is serviced by multiple instances of the software **on multiple machines**.
9. Situations where the software takes **too much memory or takes too long** to respond.
10. General **DOM** Problem: a bug related to web page rendering and interaction